

A new phenotypic screen to map quantitative trait loci associated with rice tolerance for planthoppers

P. Kadirvel, Centre for Plant Breeding and Genetics; M. Maheswaran, Centre for Plant Molecular Biology; R.P. Soundararajan and K. Gunathilagaraj, Department of Entomology, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore 641003, India

There has been a long history of attempts to design screening tests to measure plant resistance to insects since the time Painter (1951) classified plant resistance into three mechanisms: nonpreference (antixenosis), antibiosis, and tolerance. As the most important insect pests of rice (*Oryza sativa* L.), brown planthopper *Nilaparvata lugens* (Stål) and whitebacked planthopper *Sogatella furcifera* (Horvath) demanded the attention of entomologists and breeders to develop easy and reliable screening techniques to screen a large number of germplasm and breeding materials to develop cultivars with improved resistance to planthoppers (Heinrichs et al 1985). Tolerance is the most important component of resistance for breeding, but it has not been well used as the phenomenon of tolerance has not been fully understood, there is a lack of suitable techniques to identify and incorporate tolerance into an improved genetic background, and details of the genetics of tolerance have not been determined (Velusamy and Heinrichs 1986).

Panda and Heinrichs (1983) described some tolerance tests: functional plant loss index, tolerance index, antibiosis index, and plant dry weight loss per milligram of insect dry weight produced for BPH. Although various tests have been developed, the availability of tests that measure the nature of resistance precisely without the influence

of another factor is still a concern and requires continuous exploration (Reese et al 1994).

Plant resistance to planthoppers in rice has been a much studied subject since 1969 when varietal resistance was established for the first time at the International Rice Research Institute (Pathak et al 1969). However, studies on genetics of resistance have always relied on a standard seedbox screening test, which can be effective only for qualitative resistance. Current research has indicated that plant resistance to planthoppers is a quantitative trait, demanding insights into the complexities of signaling and interactions among host and pest genomes. This situation underscores the need for addressing the gap in our understanding of resistance phenotype at the molecular, cell, and whole-plant levels. Our work is one such attempt to design a screening test that can be a more sensitive phenotypic screen for genetic analysis of tolerance for planthoppers in rice.

We hypothesized that days-to-wilt, measured as the number of days after infestation required to kill the plants, can be a sensitive phenotypic screen to identify tolerance in rice for BPH. We evaluated a subset of 94 doubled-haploid (DH) lines produced from a cross between IR64 and Azucena (Guiderdoni et al 1992), along with the parents, for days-to-wilt after planthopper infestation. A brief description of the

screening procedure is given as follows.

Days-to-wilt was measured at two plant age levels: 30 and 60 d after sowing (DW30 DAS and DW60 DAS, respectively) with an insect load of 50 first- and second-instar nymphs per plant. For DW30, 15-d-old seedlings were transplanted in 15-cm-diameter clay pots and placed inside a cylindrical mylar sheet cage (13 × 75 cm). For DW60, seedlings were transplanted in 30-cm-diameter clay pots and put in a 25 × 90-cm mylar cage. The nymphs were released on the plants and allowed to feed. The day the plant wilted completely was recorded.

After BPH infestation, 30-d-old IR64 plants survived up to 12.7 d; the Azucena plants survived only up to 5.3 d. The 60-d-old IR64 plants survived up to 17.7 d, whereas the Azucena plants survived up to 11.3 d. Days-to-wilt of 30-d-old DH plants ranged from 6.3 to 13 d; those of 60-d-old DH plants ranged from 8.7 to 19.7 d.

Similarly, 30-d-old plants of IR64 survived up to 88 d after WBPH infestation, whereas the Azucena plants survived only up to 18.5 d. When 60-d-old plants were infested, the WBPH could not kill the IR64 plants, even beyond 90 d after infestation, but the Azucena plants wilted quickly (28 d). Days-to-wilt of 30-d-old DH lines ranged from 9 to 87.5 d, whereas those of 60-d-old plants ranged from 16 to 90 d (Table

1). The experiment was terminated 90 d after insect infestation. Therefore, 90 d was considered as the days-to-wilt of plants that survived beyond 90 d after infestation. The frequency distribution of phenotypic values of DH lines for days-to-wilt after BPH and WBPH infestation clearly indicated the quantitative nature of resistance (Fig. 1). We did a QTL analysis to test the sensitivity of days-to-wilt with respect to the genetic mechanism behind tolerance for planthoppers using 175 marker data of an IR64/Azucena DH population through Mapmaker/QTL (Lander et al 1987). Putative BPH resistance QTLs were detected on chromosomes 6 and 7, with LOD scores of 2.5 and

3.1, when 30- and 60-d-old plants were infested with BPH nymphs, respectively (Soundararajan et al 2004). Similarly, days-to-wilt after WBPH infestation also indicated the presence of possible QTLs on chromosomes 1 and 6 (Table 2, Fig. 2). These QTLs were detected with threshold values of 1.6 and 1.8 for 30- and 60-d-old plants, respectively. The low number of replications might have affected the significance levels of these QTLs. Furthermore, the detected QTLs were specific to plant age 30 and 60 d old, supporting the observation that plant age influences resistance level. Genetic analysis at the appropriate growth stage is necessary. Based on these results, we propose that days-to-wilt after

insect infestation could be a sensitive phenotypic screen to detect QTLs associated with resistance to planthoppers.

References

- Guiderdoni E, Galinato E, Luistro J, Vergara J. 1992. Anther culture of tropical japonica x indica hybrids of rice (*Oryza sativa* L.). *Euphytica* 62:219-224.
- Heinrichs EA, Medrano FG, Rapusas HR. 1985. Genetic evaluation for insect resistance in rice. Manila (Philippines): International Rice Research Institute. 356 p.
- Lander ES, Green P, Abrahamson J, Barlow A, Daly MJ, Lincon SE, Newburg L. 1987. Mapmaker: an interactive computer package for constructing primary genetic linkage maps of experimental and natural populations. *Genomics* 1:174-181.
- Painter RH. 1951. Insect resistance in crop plants. New York: Macmillan. 520 p.
- Panda N, Heinrichs EA. 1983. Levels of tolerance and antibiosis in rice varieties having moderate resistance to the brown planthopper, *Nilaparvata lugens* (Stål) (Hemiptera: Delphacidae). *Environ. Entomol.* 12:1204-1214.
- Pathak MD, Cheng CH, Fortuno ME. 1969. Resistance to *Nephotettix impicticeps* and *Nilaparvata lugens* in varieties of rice. *Nature* 223:502-504.
- Reese JC, Schwenke JR, Lamont PS, Zehr DD. 1994. Importance of and quantification of plant tolerance in crop pest management programmes for aphids: green bug resistance in sorghum. *J. Agric. Entomol.* 11:255-270.
- Soundararajan RP, Kadirvel P, Gunathilagaraj K, Maheswaran M. 2004. Mapping of QTLs associated with resistance to brown planthopper (*Nilaparvata lugens* Stål) by means of a doubled haploid population in rice. *Crop Sci.* 44:2214-2220.
- Velusamy R, Heinrichs EA. 1986. Tolerance in crop plants to insects. *Insect Sci. Appl.* 7(6):689-696.

Table 1. Phenotypic values of parents and DH lines of IR64/Azucena cross for resistance to planthoppers.

Trait	Parents ^a		DH lines		
	IR64	Azucena	Mean	SD	Range
Days-to-wilt (30 DAS) after BPH infestation	12.7	5.3	9	1.3	6.3–13.0
Days-to-wilt (60 DAS) after BPH infestation	17.7	11.3	14	2.2	8.7–19.7
Days-to-wilt (30 DAS) after WBPH infestation ^b	88.0	18.5	28.9	18.8	9–>90
Days-to-wilt (60 DAS) after WBPH infestation	>90	28.0	48.5	23.5	14–>90

^aMean of two replicates. ^bDays from infestation to complete wilting of plant; >90, not wilted on 90th day after infestation.

Table 2. Putative QTLs identified for various traits associated with resistance to planthoppers in IR64/Azucena DH populations of rice.

Trait ^a	Marker interval	Chromosome	LOD	Variance (%)	Additive ^b
Days-to-wilt after BPH infestation (30 DAS)	Pgi2–pRD10B	6	2.5	14.3	–0.5
Days-to-wilt after BPH infestation (60 DAS)	RG773–CDO59	7	3.1	17.6	1.1
Days-to-wilt after WBPH infestation (30 DAS)	WI–RG173	1	1.6	11.6	–7.9
Days-to-wilt after WBPH infestation (60 DAS)	RG172–Cat-1	6	1.8	8.8	–7.8

^aPutative BPH resistance QTLs are presented here on the basis of the findings of Soundararajan et al (2004). ^bEffect of Azucena allele.

Fig. 1. Frequency distribution of DH lines of IR64/Azucena cross for days-to-wilt after planthopper infestation.

Fig. 2. Linkage map showing chromosomal locations of putative QTLs detected for tolerance for planthoppers.

Application of herbicide lethality in hybrid rice

Q.S. Zhu, Q.J. Yang, D.W. Zhang, S.M. Wang, J. Dong, C. Feng, and J.B. Zhu, Green Food Research Institute, Anhui Academy of Agriculture Sciences, Hefei, Anhui, 230031, China E-mail: zhuqisheng0551@163.com

With improved seed production technology and parental out-crossing traits, hybrid rice seed production yield has increased from hundreds of kilograms per hectare to a national average of 2.5 t ha⁻¹ during the last three decades in China. However, current seed production protocols are based on a technology established 30 years ago—female and male parents are separately transplanted in different rows at a certain ratio and are harvested separately. The complexity of seed production has become a limiting factor for wide-scale adoption of hybrid rice as more labor is consumed and purity control and mechanical operations are difficult.

In 1984, Norin 8M, a mutant from japonica rice variety Norin 8, was found to be lethally susceptible to bentazone (3-isopropyl-1H-benzo-2,1,3-thiadiazine-4(3H)-ketone-2,2-dioxide), which is an ingredient of herbicides such as “basagran,” “bentazone,” and others that are used widely in rice fields for weed control. The discovery of bentazone lethality, which was genetically controlled by a pair of recessive genes, opened the path for an innovative system of hybrid rice seed production. The key approach is to integrate the lethality trait into restorer lines, which have the same days to flowering as the cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines, so that seeds of both female and male parents can be blended, planted, or transplanted

together. After pollination, the herbicide bentazone is sprayed in the field to eliminate the male plants, leaving CMS plants bearing hybrid seeds that can be bulk-harvested. This technology simplifies the operation of seed production, employs less labor, and is adaptable to mechanical seed production on a large scale, besides increasing hybrid seed yield and purity. After 21 seasons in 10 years of breeding, we successfully developed many CMS restorer lines with bentazone lethality and with different maturities to synchronize planting of various CMS lines. Heterotic hybrids were developed using these restorer lines and were applied to commercial production.

The donor parent of the lethality trait was a mutant line contributed by Dr. G. Takeda), Norin 8M, which is lethally susceptible to bentazone. A typical japonica variety, it was used to cross with many indica restorer lines to develop restorer lines with an indica genetic background having bentazone lethality. It has the same days to flowering as that of the CMS female parent. Pedigree and backcross breeding were used. The herbicide dose study was first carried out to select the best herbicide rate that would let plants show obvious but limited damage from the chemical and would let them survive until seed harvest. The herbicide used, made by Jiansu Lulilai Co. Ltd., China, was bentazone 25% aqua. (The normal dosage recommended

by the manufacturer for rice is 3,000–6,000 mL ha⁻¹.) Experiments showed that, at heading stage, application of 600 mL ha⁻¹ of bentazone showed no damage to plants; with 900 mL ha⁻¹, plants had minor damage but recovered within 10 d after herbicide spraying. However, with 1,200–1,800 mL ha⁻¹, the plants showed obvious damage 7 d after spraying and the panicles died after 10 d. At a dose of 2,700–3,600 mL ha⁻¹, obvious damage was observed in the plants by the 4th day after spraying and the whole plant died 10 d after spraying.

In the course of breeding, 900 mL bentazone ha⁻¹ was applied to screen plants with susceptibility at the panicle initiation stage in every breeding generation from F₂. Selection on the basis of phenotype was started on the 7th day after herbicide treatment. Herbicide susceptibility, along with other agronomic traits, was selected following the same selection criteria used in a general restorer line breeding program. The trait days to flowering was specifically noted because of the required flowering synchronization with female parents. Different CMS lines were planted along with R lines to provide a reference of days to flowering. The selected R lines were harvested as single plants, advanced to the next generation, and then testcrossed with various CMS lines to make hybrids for evaluation of restoration ability, combining ability, and yield (heterosis). Table 1 shows

the characteristics of the selected R lines used in the herbicide dosage study.

The selected hybrid varieties with high yield potential and acceptable quality were advanced to provincial or national yield trials and tested for commercial hybrid seed production. Many restorer lines with bentazone lethality in various indica genetic backgrounds and related commercial hybrids have now been developed. One of the good performers, hybrid “Green Rice # 5”, has gained nationwide ac-

ceptance and is being commercialized. In a farmer’s yield trial in 2004, it produced 11.45 t ha⁻¹ and outyielded, by 1.52 t ha⁻¹, the best hybrid check, Shanyou 63, the most widely grown hybrid in China. It had a 15.3% yield advantage but the same maturity.

In a 2004 seed production study, two systems—conventional seed production (row ratio of 1 male: 5 females, separate transplanting) and mixed transplanting (seed ratio of 1 male: 5 females, mixed transplanting)—were evaluated. Results showed that the mixed method produced 2.0 t ha⁻¹ more hybrid seeds than

did the conventional method, with a 42.6% yield increase (Table 2). All yield components in the mixed method had different levels of increase, but the most significant increase was in seed set rate, which was 25% higher than in the conventional method.

By using molecular marker technology, the lethality trait has been mapped in the rice genome. In future development of lines with bentazone lethality, it will be very helpful to apply market-assisted selection to speed up and increase the accuracy of the selection process.

Table 1. Lethality of R line 2E06, Hefei, 2004.

Herbicide dose (mL ha ⁻¹)	Fertile spikelets (%)	Plants surviving (%)
0	82.1	98.4
4,500	32.1	46.3
6,000	28.7	17.7
7,500	27.5	6.7
9,000	19.1	1.1
10,500	10.5	0.3
12,000	1.2	0.0

Table 2. Comparison of hybrid seed production methods, Hefei, 2004.

Method	Plants ha ⁻¹ (no. × 1,000)	Effective panicles ha ⁻¹ (no. × 1,000)	Total spikelets panicle ⁻¹ (no.)	Seed set (%)	1,000-grain weight (g)	Yield (t ha ⁻¹)
Conventional (C)	18.5	218	192.2	47.0	22	4.7
Mixed planting (M)	20.0	260	199.4	58.9	22	6.7
Increase (M - C)	1.5	42	7.2	11.9	0	2.0
Increase (%)	8.1	19.3	3.5	25.3	0	42.6

